

Recommendations and actions from the Landscaping

Day 2: Landscaping recommendations and discussion points

This document includes the information that will form the basis of the discussions of day 2 for the three stakeholder groups

- A: DNA and biodiversity data publishers
- B: Reference libraries, bioinformatics, and taxonomic systems (data)
- C: Biobanks and culture collections, and taxonomic systems (concepts)

These stakeholder discussions will each follow their own agenda, but all will largely be based on the Landscaping report (see the links in the [README](#) to the report and to the separate images of the current and future landscapes): its recommendations and suggested actions.

Therefore, here we summarise those recommendations and outline the discussion points for each stakeholder breakout: see in the three tabs on the left (when viewed online).

On the basis of your feedback during these sessions, we will be making recommendations, certainly to our funders (EU's Horizon programme) but generally to the DNA and biodiversity data community, about what needs to be done and how it can be achieved, in a practical, sustainable, realistic way.

A. DNA and biodiversity data publishers

DNA and biodiversity data publishers

The following is a summary of the recommendations from the Landscaping exercise to move from the current landscape to a smoother, more interoperable and connected landscape.

These recommendations have been split into different topics and are provided with examples for these two types of data publishers. These form the basis of the discussion that will take place in the Stakeholder session on day 2 for DNA and biodiversity data publishers.

For each section here, we would like comments on the following in the “post-its” on the miro board

- Do you agree or disagree with our recommendations? Why?
- What do you foresee as being the enablers and bottlenecks to these recommendations being taken up by the responsible stakeholders?
- Are these recommendations currently a low/high priority for you, or will be in the future? If not a priority, why - what is necessary for them to become a priority?
- Which stakeholders do you think are responsible for enacting the recommendations, and why?
- How could we encourage / reward actions undertaken to answer the recommendations?
- Anything else?

The direct link to our Miro board is:

https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVJ_vUldM=?share_link_id=778344809234. PLEASE DO NOT go to the board before the workshop starts!

Metadata (discovery, provenance, and within datasets)

1. Expanding the mandatory metadata. Within metadata record and/or within datasets
 - a. The mandatory fields will depend on type of data, type of DNA (e.g. metabarcoding vs barcoding). There will be some differences in these fields for the different types of DNA data – not just e.g. metabarcoding vs qPCR but also raw sequence vs ASV. We think that the [FAIRe checklists](#) are good to be followed here. We do suggest these common mandatory fields
 - i. Location (coordinates, bounding box), sample collection date (ISO format), depth (for marine, incl. units)
 - ii. dataset contact name and email (either a person, an institute, a helpdesk: something long-lived)
 - iii. sample type (taxonomic name or material keyword from a vocabulary)
 - iv. environmental keywords (habitat)
 - v. protocols (for all of sampling and processing; molecular work, sequencing platform/instrument and inputs, QC, bioinformatics code and inputs; all given as URLs/DOIs to open access document)
 - vi. target gene / gene region / target taxonomic assay

- vii. link to preceding data's metadata (i.e. taxon lists link to ASVs link to sequences link to material samples)
 - b. Need to be easily updateable
 - c. *There are many data publishers that now do require much of these properties, and that is fantastic.*
 - d. *We acknowledge that there will always be missing metadata from historical records, and suggest that some kind of flag to indicate that this is the reason for those missing values would be valuable (at least at an admin and data scientist level). To fill in those missing values with e.g. AI-assisted tools is feasible, but clearly would need dedicated (and new) resources.*
 - e. **Addresses: Findability, Reusability of data and metadata**
2. Require use of vocabularies and URIs in all relevant fields, in data and metadata.
- a. All fields that can point to external information (protocols, preceding data) should be required to be web addresses (URIs)
 - b. All vocabulary fields should be given as URIs (over PIDs) and never as only plain strings. *But how do we make these values then also human-understandable? Suggestions?*
 - c. **Addresses: Interoperability, Reusability of data and metadata**
3. "Checklists" of the (meta)data that needs to be present so that the data are suitable for particular types of use.
- a. Some potential types of checklists could be for:
 - i. Biodiversity research
 - ii. Invasive species monitoring
 - iii. Biocommunity composition research
 - iv. For particular mandated monitoring purposes
 - v. GOOS-compliant
 - b. **Addresses: Findability, Reusability of data**
4. Stronger requirements for providing provenance metadata.
- a. To be provided as additional to the current metadata and intimately linked to the dataset (e.g. download the data, get provenance as well)
 - b. To describe all the relevant steps that lead to *that* dataset – a “repeat the experiment recipe”
 - c. All the who (agents), what (instruments, storage, transporting, software, input data), where (location, depth, address), when (date of each step), how (protocols, procedures, software inputs, QC), and why(project/study purpose).
 - d. Would require development of provenance templates for the different types of data
 - e. **Addresses: Findability, Reusability of data**

Data formatting and machine-accessibility and -understandability

- 5. Provide and enforce use of data templates that result in interoperable data
 - a. For spreadsheets, require ISO formatted dates, locations, URIs over PID over strings, specifically include units

- b. Many publishers already do this (GBIF, OBIS, Pangaea among others)
 - i. We suggest everyone does this
 - ii. We suggest the templates are easier to find and follow → can potentially be incorporated directly in code
 - iii. We suggest that coordination on data templates between different data providers will help achieve greater interoperability and less fatigue/confusion for the scientists
 - iv. We suggest that the formatting of the entries (values, strings) in the templates is more strict, and that units are specifically given in data rather than hard-coded (greater machine-understandability)
- c. **Addresses: Interoperability, Reusability of data, and wider uptake**
- 6. Improve machine-understandability of (meta)data by using terms taken from vocabularies and checklists, use of machine-understandable schemas for (meta)data templates, etc. This is about machine-understandability, not just developer-understandability. This facilitates, allows automation of, (meta)data sharing between stakeholders
 - a. This is about
 - i. Requiring the use of web addresses ([CoolURIs](#)) over PIDs (persistent IDs) and strings for terms taken from a vocabulary or checklist, in both the data and the metadata you accept from data providers and provide to data users but (see comment from 2b above)
 - ii. Making it very easy to find out what standards, vocabularies and templates you use for (meta)data ingestion, (meta)data sharing, metadata publishing, data downloading. A standardised way for everyone to publish this info on their website would be less frustrating for users
 - iii. Providing that information in a machine-consumable way so that it can be incorporated in bioinformatics code easily, and can be used by data harvesters and automated analyses (e.g. AI) more easily. For example, to describe a CVS file one can use [CSVW](#) and [Croissant](#)
 - b. **Addresses: Interoperability, Reusability of data, and wider uptake**
- 7. Expose your metadata and checklists and vocabularies as linked open data
 - a. This means to publish your metadata not just as XML files to be click-downloaded, or accessible via APIs, but also in RDF for direct machine-accessibility and understandability
 - b. Good examples: [BODC's NVS](#) and [Marine Regions](#) have LDES (linked data event stream) feeds that expose all their terms in RDF
 - c. **Addresses: Interoperability, Reusability of data, and allows automated access to all the data with one method and in one place**

Cooperation between stakeholders on sharing and standards

- 8. Publish local, share on to regional/thematic, and finally share on to global:

- a. It is an efficient way to work – spread the effort – and engages the local communities better, and often matches requirements from local funding agencies (?)
 - b. Allows for 2-way communication and 2-ways sharing of standards (?)
 - c. More, easier to find, information on how this works on websites is recommended
 - d. Should always end up publishing in global repositories – this is a global science!
 - e. **Addresses: Findability, Accessibility, Reusability of data**
9. DNA and Biodiversity data publishers to regularly work together on standards and approaches.
- a. Would be those used in and for data and metadata, for example
 - i. vocabularies (terms and their definitions)
 - ii. data formats
 - iii. data formatting within data
 - iv. metadata formats
 - v. metadata schemas
 - vi. Mandatory vs recommended vs optional data fields
 - b. Already done by many, but not by all and not at all levels of detail
 - c. *Will require*
 - i. EITHER a cross-mapping of all publishers vocabularies, schemas etc. to that of all other publishers
 - ii. OR (better!) mapping each to one community-defined set of standards and schemas → to accommodate all differences while providing a layer of commonality
 - iii. *How to initiate and maintain this?*
 - d. **Addresses: Findability, Accessibility, Reusability of data**

Taxonomic- and bioinformatics-related issues

10. Implement key Quality Control checks to validate the eDNA occurrence data in their databases and ensure the correct reuse by non-eDNA experts.
- a. Identify the key aspects of eDNA-derived occurrences that all biodiversity scientists need to be aware of when using occurrences (and not themselves reprocessing anything), For example
 - i. were negative controls used?
 - ii. results are at less than XX% confidence level
 - b. Then add flags to data in OBIS, GBIF etc to convey this information
 - c. **Addresses: Reusability of data**
11. Support interoperable and open data originating from bioinformatics pipelines
- a. Work with bioinformaticians to adopt standard templates for their data AND metadata outputs
 - b. Work with bioinformaticians in finding a way to link to all outputs from the processing, not just the taxonomic data
 - c. Require URI/DOI for bioinformatics codes used to produce occurrences e.g. to protocols.io or GitHub?

- d. Require open access sequencing molecular and sequencing protocols
 - e. Addresses: Interoperability and Reusability of data. + also repeatability.
12. Improve mapping of omics and linnean taxonomic naming systems so that eDNA results are more discoverable and understandable by biodiversity data users
- a. Taxonomy is acknowledged to be a thorny issue – sessions B and C are focussed on taxonomy specifically as data (how to refer to taxonomic information in data) and concepts (how to deal with “messy” species)
 - b. What we can recommend is:
 - i. to use a mainstream appropriate taxonomy where possible. (can be a niche one e.g. one covering just plants)
 - ii. that where taxonomic backbones exist and are used, that they are mapped to each other so that the name(s) and ID(s) in one system are linked to the name(s) and ID(s) in another
 - c. Addresses: Findability, Interoperability, and Reusability of data

B. Reference libraries, bioinformatics,
taxonomy

Reference libraries, bioinformatics, taxonomies (data)

The following is a summary of the recommendations from the Landscaping exercise to move from the current landscape to a smoother, more interoperable and connected landscape. These recommendations will form the basis of our breakout session B discussion, for which we will use Miro. The direct link to the Miro board we will use during this session is: https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVJ_uCvgl=/?share_link_id=290204600156. PLEASE DO NOT go to the board before the workshop starts!

Reference libraries

Recommendations for the future landscape and discussion points

1. More use of standard and machine-understandable metadata (RDF, XML), standard and open data (CSV over excel), with the use of vocabularies over strings and URLs over PIDs
 - a. How do we encourage uptake of this? Is providing templates and examples enough, or is some stick as well as this carrot necessary?
 - b. What authority (who) should provide any such examples and templates?
2. More assignment of URIs to the taxonomic results in the libraries (taxon names and IDs), so people can refer to that information with the URI
 - a. How do we encourage uptake of this?
3. Standardised information about the taxonomic curation done (or not done) should always be given, and this given in each metadata record/dataset (as actual text or as a link to where that info can be found)
 - a. How do we encourage uptake of this? Is providing templates and examples enough, or is some stick as well as this carrot necessary?
 - b. What authority (who) should provide any such examples and templates?
4. Taxonomic identification confidence levels should always be given
 - a. Is this feasible?
5. Always publish your reference library (whether that is a formal one open to others to use, or one you created just for this project) and aim to make it open access (free to find and inspect, if not also adopt), in particular where that will be used for scientific and monitoring work. This includes the supporting omics data (ASVs etc) and the associated taxonomic information, not just the classifications.
 - a. How do we encourage uptake of this?
6. Taxonomic information or omics data that were taken from elsewhere (harvested data, taxon names from some existing backbone), should always be referenced in the data/metadata as a URI (for reusability, traceability)
 - a. How do we encourage uptake of this?
7. Develop the mentality that acknowledgement and sustainable funding should be provided to the scientists and organisations that do this work; funding for taking

existing systems and making those FAIR (backwards-engineering) should be made available. Sustainable is especially important as information about genes, the gene data itself, about taxonomic assignments and names, is changing all the time: we need to avoid that one cannot trace past discoveries to what we now know better about them

- a. How can we push the funders and research organisations into doing this?
Who are the best agents to approach?

Bioinformatics

Recommendations for the future landscape and discussion points

1. Bioinformatics code should always be published: its metadata records, its metadata description (e.g. CodeMeta, FAIR checklist). This does not mean free to use, just free to find. These discovery and description metadata should always have a URI (e.g. zenodo) and be open access (with acknowledgement and/or with registration requirements is allowed under open access).
2. There should be a formalised, machine-readable metadata descriptions of code (e.g. CodeMeta, FAIR)
 - a. Can we WG to develop a profile and templates for bioinformatics code and to promote uptake?
3. All bioinformatics codes should be FAIR – there are profiles for software to make them FAIR e.g. having a CodeMeta.json standardised description, the need to have test cases and test results, documentation not just of how to run but of the output files and of the data in the output files, etc. We can do this particularly for bioinformatics
 - a. How do we encourage uptake of this? Is providing templates and examples enough, or is some stick as well as this carrot necessary?
 - b. What authority (who) should provide any such recommendations and templates?
 - c. What training courses, templates, material is available?
4. All intermediate products should be published
 - a. But what are the practical ways that this can be done? Given issues with volume and size, where to publish these data, how to help people navigate those data for each different code?
5. Output data should be FAIR - interoperable (e.g. CSV), reusable (provenance of the running of the code meaning input files and settings when the code was run, version, date, etc), documented (explain what is in the CSV), and must include taxonomic IDs as URLs not just names
 - a. How do we encourage uptake of this? Is providing templates and examples enough, or is some stick as well as this carrot necessary?
 - b. What authority (who) should provide any such recommendations and templates?

Taxonomic systems / backbones (data)

Discussion points

1. As a number of different systems are used to give taxonomic names/IDs to organisms, it is important that formalised, documented, sustained, and machine-readable mapping between the information (names/IDs) from these systems is maintained → for WORMS and NCBI, is this done as “when we have funding” or “as part of our core remit/funding”. What are the bottlenecks to this activity
2. All taxonomic names should have URIs (rather than URLs - looking at you here, NCBI; and rather than PIDs - looking at you here, BOLD) so they can be referred to unambiguously and forever.
3. All systems should have IDs for every name in its database (even ambiguous/unidentified ones: this means decoupling the way the IDs are assigned from the nature of the name (such as its position in a taxon tree)). This is particularly so for custom reference libraries

The future landscape wants a network of connected, searchable, and reliable reference libraries.

Recommendations to improve towards this future landscape

Define and recommend essential metadata which enable a quality-control and curation:

1. These include recommendations on tracking sequence and assignment provenance to avoid artificially inflating biodiversity. By always linking taxonomic assignment to the original sequence in research data portals, we avoid problems caused by different taxonomic assignments of the same source data which are then uploaded to data research databases.
 - RO-Crate (<https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>) could be a solution, as it allows complex data to be captured in a structured form(JSON).
 - Anchor essential metadata in international methodological and laboratory standards to ensure wide adherence and their uptake.
2. Create a recognition system of databases/libraries that follow common taxonomic curation recommendations (*a topic discussed in Stakeholder group C*)
 - This could help them to obtain funding to be sustainable. The lack of long term funding for the curation of reference databases is a problem, especially as this is a field where knowledge is evolving rapidly. A certification or quality label at the EU-level where the curation of reference databases is recognised as strategically important, and databases get recognised as following the EU-level scientific curation requirements.
 - The Global Biodata Coalition (<https://globalbiodata.org>) was cited as an organisation that assesses biological databases globally → done under their arms?
3. Establish connections between recognised/curated databases so they can communicate through an integrated network.
 - Here, metadata recommendations should focus on interoperability through common metadata standard vocabulary (e.g. an improved version of the MIxS vocabulary).

- Output data in RDF (JSON-LD or similar). This makes it much easier for machines as well as humans to find and digest metadata.
 - This can be a protocol of data and metadata exchange between reference libraries. Any reference library following this exchange will be part of the network (irrespective of the country of origin). There are some existing data exchange protocols that we can borrow ideas from, e.g. HUPO-PSI.
4. Create a metadata search portal/engine to query the “accredited” reference databases that follow the eDNAqua-Plan recommendation or compliant international standards. This approach would maintain the diversity in existing databases, while ensuring common curation requirements are met for reliability.
 - Inspiration could be taken from the Genomes on a Tree metadata portal from the Earth Biogenome Project <https://goat.genomehubs.org>.
 - iBOL Europe or the European eDNA Society, which are both gaining momentum, could be a potential central hubs for this.
 5. Establish a feedback system from curators and users back to the data providers in primary platforms.
 - Currently, records in the primary databases are meant to be an archival copy. The ELIXIR Contextual Data Clearing House (CDCH) however allows the addition of annotations to ENA objects, which are shown alongside the archived records. A feedback loop is already in place between UNITE and ENA using the CDCH.
 6. How can we make metadata collection and data sharing (publishing) as easy as possible? What tricks have worked for you? Is there more we could be doing? Or could we be doing it differently? Since FAIR data training is lagging at the university / lab level, should we take on the responsibility to fill the gaps?

C. Biobanks, culture collections,
taxonomies

Biobanks, culture collections, taxonomy (concepts)

Below you will find a summary of the findings and recommendations of the Landscaping report, which forms the starting point of the discussion for today. Particular discussion points will be:

- Heterogeneity is a strength but also a challenge for integration: how can we handle heterogeneity of samples within biobanks and how can we increase interoperability across different specialised biobanks?
- Digital access and metadata: what steps can we take towards adopting common metadata standards and schemas?
- Integration of genetic and bioinformatic data: the integration of these data is uneven at present, with a lack of DNA-specific standards, storage methods, etc. How can we move towards a stronger model of traceability from sample to published data? How can we improve integration with external bioinformatic resources? And how to manage name changes in species and synonyms in different databases?
- Legal compliance and traceability (Nagoya Protocol + ABS): What best practices exist for dealing with this? Could a common network solution facilitate trust and transparency?
- Networks, collaboration, and future outlook: Many biobanks already participate in international networks. How can we strengthen European collaboration in aquatic and biodiversity biobanks? What role should we play in conservation policies, climate resilience, and biotechnology?

The direct link to the Miro board we will use during this session is:

<https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVJ804QPo=/> PLEASE DO NOT go to the board before the workshop starts!

Biobanks and Culture Collections

What does not currently work well

1. Inconsistent Data Standards and Formats. Adopting data and metadata standards that are interoperable (to machines and humans) and open, at least for the data that you chose to publish. More use of LIMS.
2. Limited Information Sharing. Share more information.
 - This can be achieved by exposing data in the database as [RDF](#) and sharing as [LOD](#) (linked open data), hence not needing to rebuild existing data-serving interfaces. At the same time, these data would be made more interoperable (a feature of RDF) by greater use of vocabularies (over strings) and URIs (over strings or PIDs).
 - May require policy decisions to be made.
3. Inadequate Sample Traceability. Collection permits and metadata are often stored separately from samples, complicating compliance with e.g. Nagoya Protocol: better

linking between databases is recommended. Systematically track research outputs derived from your samples (demonstrate impact).

4. Variable Growth in DNA Service Demand.
5. Emerging DNA Management Practices.
6. Limited DNA-Specific Metadata Standards. Adopt and where necessary, expand those that already exist → possibly requiring a working group on this (together with all other stakeholders at this w/s)
7. Variable DNA Storage Methodologies. Harmonise.
8. Incomplete Integration with Bioinformatics Resources.
9. Taxonomic Information Challenges. The varied taxonomic reference systems used by different biobanks can create challenges when comparing or integrating DNA data across institutions, particularly for less-studied organisms or those with complex taxonomic histories.
10. Underrepresentation of Certain Taxa. Samples from threatened or rare species are frequently insufficient, and strategies to replenish or amplify DNA are not consistently applied. In general, for macroorganisms, only a small part of the described species is deposited in biobanks or culture collections. Further, for specific ecosystem types, microbial diversity is often underrepresented due to culturing difficulties.
11. Limited Backup and Redundancy.

Recommendations for the future

1. Institutions need to continue to be actively working toward digital accessibility.
2. Most institutions need to improve workflow tracking (e.g. Laboratory Information Management Systems LIMS).
3. Most also generally need to move towards databases (away from Excel), to continue the digital transformation.
4. Some institutions could also increase the amount of data that they share.
 - E.g. Most institutions need to provide detailed metadata about advanced genomic and bioinformatic workflows.
5. To use more standards, to allow increased interoperability and thus de facto harmonisation:
 - DNA-specific metadata standards
 - Taxonomic
6. A suggestion is to have a quality label where an institutional BioBank is complying with appropriate good practice and standards. *This is to be more specific (and omics-focussed) than the current ISO standards for biobanks (e.g. ISO 20387:2018)*

Taxonomic systems / backbones (concepts)

Discussion points

1. Taxonomic annotations used in genetic reference databases are variable and have no central standard. Agree and define; a system that is flexible to possible future needs. A copy from the points in the Landscape “what does not work”:

- As more genetic information becomes available, higher level taxonomic names increasingly follow a cladistic system as opposed to the traditional systems like the one of Linné. At higher taxonomic levels, least common ancestors are increasingly difficult to identify meaning that taxonomic changes at these levels (class, phylum or even kingdom) are expected to continue for the foreseeable future.
 - The increasing adoption of cladistic systematics has led to an increased use of intermediate taxonomic levels in order to communicate about well-known taxonomic groups. For example, flatfishes are not grouped anymore in their own order (former Pleuronectiformes) but as a sub-order (Pleuronectoidei) of jacks (Carangiformes).
 - As another example, PR2 recently changed the way they annotate their sequences from eight to nine taxonomic levels (<https://pr2-database.org/post/news/2023-04-06-pr2-version-5.0/>)
 - The number of taxonomic levels may differ by field. While in botany, cultivars have their own taxonomic rank at the infraspecific level, the subspecies concept has been almost abandoned for fishes. In other vertebrate groups, however, subspecific epithets are still widely used (e.g. for reptiles).
 - The need for taxonomic levels may vary depending on the diversity in a specific group. For example, the family of Cichlidae has more than 2000 species and subfamily and tribe names are frequently used in the scientific literature to facilitate communication. In contrast, the sister taxon of Cichlidae, the Pholidichthyidae, includes only two extant species that belong to the same genus rendering subfamily and tribe names obsolete.
 - All the reference databases use a different format (or fasta header), which makes it complicated to make general purpose pipelines, let alone be sure they are comparable with each other
2. Conciliation of data on classical (morphotaxonomic) taxonomic assignments and DNA-based taxonomic assignments. When organisms have been morphologically identified as belonging to a group that is now considered polyphyletic, the scientific name should be changed to a higher level taxon.

The future landscape wants a network of connected, searchable, and reliable reference libraries.

Recommendations to improve towards this future landscape

1. Define and recommend common taxonomic curation principles:
 - The taxonomic community (experts who identify, name, describe, and classify biodiversity working from the level of molecules, including eDNA and eRNA, genomes and metagenomes, species and populations, to habitats and ecosystems), are vital: ensure that its capacity to engage with and support policy and other decision-making are strengthened and funded.
 - Of relevance: iBOL-Europe alongside the upcoming call HORIZON-CL6-2025-01-BIODIV-03: Strengthening taxonomic approaches for biodiversity.
 - Anchor minimum taxonomic curation principles in international standards.

2. Create a recognition system of databases/libraries that follow these recommendations
 - This could help them to obtain funding to be sustainable. The lack of long term funding for the curation of reference databases is a problem, especially as this is a field where knowledge is evolving rapidly. A certification or quality label at the EU-level where the curation of reference databases is recognised as strategically important, and databases get recognised as following the EU-level scientific curation requirements.
 - The Global Biodata Coalition (<https://globalbiodata.org>) was cited as an organisation that assesses biological databases globally → done under their arms?
3. Establish a feedback system from curators and users back to the data providers in primary platforms.
 - Currently, records in the primary databases are meant to be an archival copy. The ELIXIR Contextual Data Clearing House (CDCH) however allows the addition of annotations to ENA objects, which are shown alongside the archived records. A feedback loop is already in place between UNITE and ENA using the CDCH.